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Abstract. The paper analyzes the sport activity among athletes during pandemic period. It is well known, that many factors affect the physical activity and involvement of the population in mass sports, including insufficient time to engage in sports activities, low level of awareness, lack of access to appropriate infrastructure in sports facilities and open public spaces, lack of qualified staff and other problems. Research aims to determine the problems of less involvement of young generation in sport activities and physical exercises. The number of sports organizations, clubs and sports units in Georgia has increased over the last ten years. It is important for the state to support sports activities and involve more young people in the sports activities of school and higher or vocational students. Received outcomes showed that about 50% of the respondents exercised with moderate intensity in conditions of self-isolation, which is a positive indicator. According to them, the population is aware of the therapeutic impact of sports activity and exercise, but it is doubtful whether the youth and adolescents are able to lead a healthy lifestyle and exercise, especially during the pandemic.

Key words: sport activity, youth, exercises, healthy lifestyle.

Introduction. About 25% of the population of Georgia are young people aged 15-29. The behaviors formed during adolescence can have a critical impact on both their lives and the future of society as a whole. Despite the recent positive developments, it is clear that adolescents and young people face many problems [1].

The low physical activity of the population in Georgia and consequently insufficient participation in sports exercises and sport competitions are recorded in various studies. The study of non-communicable disease risk factors of 2016 found that 82.4% of the population aged 18 to 69 years were not intensively engaged in physical activity (men - 72.2%, women - 91.8%) [4].

Many factors are known to affect the physical activity and involvement of the population in mass sports, including: insufficient time to engage in sports activities, low level of awareness, lack of access to appropriate infrastructure in sports facilities and open public spaces, lack of qualified staff and other problems.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), physical inactivity is the fourth leading risk factor for death, with more than three million deaths worldwide each year. A sedentary lifestyle is believed to be a problem for adolescents and young adults, although according to WHO, physical inactivity poses a serious threat to the health of older and older people as well.

Objectives - The aim of our study was to determine how active young people were involved in sports or physical activity in response to the spread of New Coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) infection (COVID-19).

Research materials and methods. The research was conducted based on the analysis of the existing scientific literature. To solve this problem, we conducted an observation and survey with the involvement of young athletes.

Research Results. We conducted a survey during the active period of distribution of COVID-19 athletes in the field of physical education and rehabilitation, as well as in the coaching staff. The study focused on maintaining exercise and adequate physical activity. The study found that about half of the respondents exercised with moderate intensity in conditions of self-isolation, which is a positive indicator. According to them, the population is aware of the therapeutic impact of sports activity and exercise, but it is doubtful whether the youth and adolescents are able to lead a healthy lifestyle and exercise, especially during the pandemic.

Discussion. The reason for low physical activity among young people is the time factor and the lack / inaccessibility of adequate free infrastructure. Sports activity and a healthy lifestyle are quite low in young people, which leads to delays in their physical and mental development and instability to many diseases. It is important to mention, that there are mainly five ways to support sport activities in young generation. It is physical activity, living healthy lifestyle, create access to sport equipment, provide special environment for youth development, make sure that kids are safe while participating in sport activities [3].

Also, sports activities and exercises are a great necessity for young people. Interestingly, the United Nations (UN) views sport not only as a human right but also as a unique concept that incorporates many fundamental human principles: "Sport has a unique power to attract, unite and inspire people" [2].

The number of sports organizations, clubs and sports units in Georgia has increased over the last ten years. It is important for the state to support sports activities and involve more young people in the sports activities of school and higher or vocational students.

Conclusion. Based on the data obtained by us, it can be assumed that it is not enough to increase the number of gyms, clubs, it is necessary to take measures aimed at youth involvement and in this regard the Georgian State University of Physical Education and Sports should be activated by training qualified staff and developing scientifically based recommendations. For the Ministry of Sports and Youth.

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